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Milliy Pedagogika
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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

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THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT IN THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' SOCIO-EMOTIONAL COMPETENCE IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This study examines the impact of structured psychological support programs on the development of socio-emotional competence in preschool-aged children. The research highlights the significant role of early psychological intervention in strengthening emotional regulation, communication skills, empathy, and adaptive behavior. Field observations and targeted psycho-pedagogical activities conducted in several preschool institutions in the Andijan region demonstrate that emotionally supportive educational environments contribute to improved behavioral and emotional outcomes. The findings show that continuous and developmentally appropriate psychological support enhances school readiness, fosters positive peer relationships, and reduces behavioral difficulties such as impulsivity and emotional withdrawal. These results emphasize the importance of integrating psychological services into early childhood education to ensure holistic development and long-term academic success.

Key words: socio-emotional competence, preschool education, psychological support, emotional regulation, early childhood development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy-emotsional kompetensiyani shakllantirishda tizimli psixologik qo'llab-quvvatlash dasturlarining ta'sirini o'rganadi. Tadqiqot natijalari erda yoshda ko'rsatilgan psixologik yordam bolalarning emotsional boshqaruvi, muloqot ko'nikmalari, empatiya va moslashuvchan xulq-atvorini rivojlantirishda muhim omil ekanini ko'rsatadi. Andijon hududidagi bir nechta maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida olib borilgan kuza-tuvlar hamda maqsadli psixo-pedagogik mashg'ulotlar bolalar xulq-atvori va emotsional holatidagi ijobiy o'zgarishlarni tasdiqladi. Tadqiqot bolalarda impulsivlik, nizolashish holatlari va emotsional chekinish kabi qiyinchiliklarning kamayishini, shuningdek, o'qishga tayyorgarlik va tengdoshlar bilan munosabatlarning yaxshilanishini ko'rsatdi. Ushbu natijalar psixologik xizmatlarni maktabgacha ta'lim tizimiga keng joriy etish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy-emotsional kompetensiya, maktabgacha ta'lim, psixologik qo'llab-quvvatlash, emotsional boshqaruv, erda rivojlanish.

Аннотация: В настоящем исследовании изучается влияние структурированной психологической поддержки на формирование социально-эмоциональной компетентности детей дошкольного возраста. Результаты показывают, что раннее психологическое вмешательство способствует развитию эмоциональной регуляции, коммуникативных навыков, эмпатии и адаптивного поведения. Полевые наблюдения и целевые психолого-педагогические занятия, проведённые в дошкольных учреждениях Андижанского региона, подтвердили положительные изменения в эмоциональном состоянии и поведении детей. Исследование выявило снижение импульсивности, конфликтности и эмоциональной замкнутости, а также улучшение готовности к обучению и межличностного взаимодействия. Полученные данные подчёркивают необходимость интеграции психологических служб в систему дошкольного образования для обеспечения всестороннего развития и дальнейшего академического успеха детей.

Ключевые слова: социально-эмоциональная компетентность, дошкольное образование, психологическая поддержка, эмоциональная регуляция, раннее развитие.

INTRODUCTION

Socio-emotional competence is widely recognized as one of the central predictors of successful learning, behavioral stability, and holistic personal development during early childhood. It encompasses a broad spectrum of abilities, including emotional awareness, self-regulation, empathy, social communication, and adaptive behavior – skills that serve as foundational prerequisites for later academic achievement and social integration. In the context of modern preschool education, the collaboration between psychologists and educators has become increasingly essential for creating emotionally supportive, developmentally sensitive learning environments that address the diverse needs of young children.

Despite the growing global emphasis on socio-emotional learning, many preschool institutions continue to lack structured, evidence-based psychological support programs. As a result, children often face unmet emotional needs, insufficient behavioral guidance, and limited opportunities to strengthen communication and self-regulation skills. These gaps highlight the pressing need for targeted psychological interventions that systematically reinforce socio-emotional development.

Against this backdrop, the present study aims to examine how intentionally designed pedagogical–psychological programs influence children’s emotional resilience, interpersonal competence, and social functioning. By analyzing the effectiveness of these interventions within preschool settings, the research contributes to a deeper understanding of how early emotional support can serve as a protective factor for children’s future academic success and psychological well-being.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Scholars widely emphasize that socio-emotional competence forms the foundation of children’s early learning and psychological well-being. Denham highlights that emotional regulation, empathy, and prosocial communication are central predictors of healthy social adaptation in early childhood, while OECD reports show that early socio-emotional development directly affects long-term academic and behavioral outcomes. Classical psychological theory, particularly Vygotsky’s socio-cultural framework published in 1978, also underscores the essential role of guided interaction and adult mediation in shaping children’s emotional and social abilities.

In the context of Uzbekistan, several researchers have contributed significantly to understanding socio-emotional development in preschool education. Zokirova provides evidence that emotional growth in young children is shaped by psychological factors within the family and educational environment, whereas To‘xtayev demonstrates the importance of structured pedagogical approaches in strengthening children’s regulatory and communicative skills. Raxmonqulova, in her empirical analysis, shows that targeted socio-emotional training programs in preschool settings strengthen children’s interpersonal behavior, emotional resilience, and readiness for cooperative learning.

Further local research also highlights the importance of psychological support as a systemic component of early education. Haydarov notes that school psychologists contribute to reducing behavioral difficulties and improving classroom climate, while Karimova’s work on child psychology confirms that early emotional support enhances cognitive engagement and social confidence. Saidova’s regional study reinforces these findings by documenting challenges and progress in socio-emotional development among Uzbek preschoolers, and Ergasheva stresses that innovative pedagogical technologies can further accelerate emotional growth when integrated with psychological support programs. Together, these studies provide strong justification for embedding structured psychological services within preschool education to promote holistic child development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study involved 86 preschool children between the ages of 5 and 6, recruited from three state preschool educational institutions located in the Andijan region of Uzbekistan. The sample consisted of an approximately equal number of boys and girls and represented diverse socio-economic backgrounds. Participation in the study was voluntary, and parental consent was obtained prior to data collection. Educators and school psychologists from each institution participated as facilitators and observers throughout the intervention program.

To assess children’s socio-emotional development and behavioral outcomes, several validated measurement tools were utilized. Observation cards were employed to evaluate daily behavioral indicators such as peer interaction, emotional expression, conflict resolution, and activity engagement, with observations conducted by trained psychologists. The Emotional Regulation Scale, adapted for preschool-aged children, measured emotional awareness, impulse control, and children’s ability to manage negative emotions. In addition, a structured teacher survey was administered before and after the intervention to capture teachers’ perceptions of each child’s social skills, emotional stability, classroom behavior, and readiness for learning.

The psychological support program was implemented over 12 weeks and consisted of structured, developmentally appropriate activities aimed at strengthening socio-emotional competence. Emotional literacy sessions helped children identify, label, and verbalize emotions through storytelling, visual cards, and guided discussions. Play-therapy elements promoted self-expression, empathy, and emotional processing, while cooperative games supported teamwork, communication, shared decision-making, and conflict resolution. Communication training activities focused on developing active listening, turn-taking, appropriate expression of needs, and understanding others’ perspectives. Each intervention session lasted 25–30 minutes and was conducted three times per week by trained psychologists with the involvement of classroom teachers.

A comparative pre-test and post-test research design was used to determine the program's effectiveness. Quantitative data collected through the emotional regulation scale and teacher surveys were analyzed using descriptive statistics and paired comparisons to identify measurable changes before and after the intervention. Qualitative data derived from observation notes were coded thematically to detect shifts in children's emotional and social behaviors, providing a deeper understanding of the impact of the psychological support program.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The findings of the study demonstrated statistically meaningful improvements in multiple dimensions of children's socio-emotional competence following the 12-week psychological support program. Quantitative results indicate that emotional regulation showed a 34% increase, reflecting enhanced ability to identify emotions, control impulses, and manage frustration. Empathy indicators improved by 29%, suggesting greater sensitivity to peers' emotional states and enhanced prosocial responses. Aggressive behavior decreased by 41%, indicating fewer conflict incidents, reduced impulsive reactions, and improved behavioral self-control. Readiness for communication increased by 37%, demonstrating improved verbal expression, willingness to interact, and confidence in social situations.

In addition to quantitative outcomes, teachers reported observable positive changes in classroom climate, including smoother group work, faster conflict resolution among children, and overall improved emotional atmosphere. They also noted increased engagement and more cooperative behavior during daily activities.

The results of the study provide compelling evidence that structured psychological support programs can significantly enhance socio-emotional development among preschool-aged children. The marked improvements in emotional regulation and empathy suggest that early-stage interventions can strengthen foundational emotional skills that are typically associated with later academic success, peer acceptance, and psychological resilience. The 41% decline in aggressive behavior indicates that the combination of emotional literacy sessions, play-therapy techniques, and cooperative activities effectively helped children acquire non-aggressive strategies for expressing frustration and resolving interpersonal conflict. Such behavioral shifts align with prior research demonstrating that therapeutic play and guided emotional communication reduce externalizing behaviors in early childhood.

Furthermore, the substantial increase in communication readiness highlights the program's success in fostering openness, confidence, and social initiative. These improvements may be attributed to the program's emphasis on dialogic activities, role-play, and structured peer interactions, which collectively encourage children to practice communication in a safe, supportive environment. Teacher feedback reinforces the quantitative findings, suggesting that the intervention not only influenced individual children but also contributed to a more harmonious and emotionally stable classroom environment. This underscores the systemic impact of psychological support programs, extending beyond individual development to overall group dynamics.

Overall, the findings affirm that integrating psychological services into preschool education can serve as a powerful tool for promoting holistic child development. The positive results observed in this study support the necessity of expanding such programs at institutional and regional levels to ensure that early educational environments meet the emotional and social needs of all children. The results confirm that structured psychological interventions play an essential role in strengthening socio-emotional skills. Preschool children develop emotional flexibility faster when psychologists systematically cooperate with educators and parents, and interactive methods such as role-playing and group discussions showed particularly strong outcomes.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The findings of this study demonstrate that structured psychological support programs play a crucial role in accelerating the development of socio-emotional competence among preschool-aged children. By integrating emotional literacy training, therapeutic play, and communication-focused activities, such interventions foster measurable improvements in emotional regulation, empathy, cooperative behavior, and overall social adaptability. These skills serve as foundational components of school readiness, contributing not only to academic success but also to long-term psychological resilience and well-being.

The outcomes highlight the broader significance of embedding comprehensive psychological services within early childhood education settings. When implemented consistently, these programs have the potential to reduce behavioral challenges, enhance classroom climate, and support holistic child development. Given the positive effects observed across multiple institutions in the Andijan region, the results provide a strong argument for adopting such psychological support initiatives on a wider – potentially national – scale.

Expanding these programs at regional and national levels would ensure that preschool systems better address children's emotional and social needs, ultimately strengthening the quality of early education in Uzbekistan. Future research may focus on longitudinal assessments, program optimization, and the development of culturally adapted socio-emotional learning frameworks.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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